

Gravitational Attraction Is Not Real

There can be only repulsions and not any attractions

Our understanding of the smallest particle is incomplete

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Abstract:

In the year 1980, I could derive a new gravitational formula based on push by the smallest particles rather than an imaginary magical attraction between the objects. The smallest particles or the energy packets, moving with the speed of light in every direction were already present before the emergence of planets of the universe, and the planets or the matter emerged by their complex groupings. The paper was copyrighted in 1983.

Later on April 22, 2019, I found from Quora.com that Le Sage's Theory was based on my hypothesis of gravitational push, which of course was not having much experimental evidence, that's why it remained ignored.

I was glad to find that one person was already supporting my hypothesis based on logical facts. Newton and Einstein have tried to explain gravitational attraction that still lacks to clarify complete working of our universe.

When people compared Le Sage's Theory with Newton's theory, they found Newton's theory more acceptable because its formula was readily available to predict (not explain) most of the motions of heavenly bodies. Le Sage's theory of gravitation is a kinetic theory of gravity originally proposed by Nicolas Fatio de Duillier in 1690 and later by Georges-Louis Le Sage in 1748. The theory proposed a mechanical explanation for Newton's gravitational force in terms of streams of tiny unseen particles (which Le Sage called ultra-mundane corpuscles) impacting all material objects from all directions.

During Le Sage's time mathematics was not so helpful to Le Sage's hypothesis and he was not able to develop a formula to calculate force of push between the objects. Also, there was no evidence of the presence of dark matter and the expansion of the universe.

Since the 1920s, astronomers have hypothesized that the universe contains more matter than seen by the naked eye or by the use of any scientific gadgets. It is noticed, by observing unexplainable movement of galaxies, that the path of motion of galaxies is being influenced by some nearby clusters of invisible matter.

On 25 August 2016, astronomers reported that Dragonfly 44, an ultra diffuse galaxy (UDG) with the mass of the Milky Way galaxy, but with nearly no star structure, is made almost entirely of dark matter.

Now, we have some more real observations to litmus test Newton's theory.

My gravitational formula predicts that the distance of Sun-Earth Lagrangian point from earth comes out to be 1370444 kilometres (1.37 million km) based on following data:

Diameter of Earth = 12742 km.

Diameter of Sun = 1.3927 million km.

Distance of Sun from Earth = 151160000 km

As per my hypothesis, the cross sectional point of two tangents between Sun and Earth is Sun-Earth Lagrange point. At this location, push particles will get absolutely nil resistance from Sun and Earth.

The Google search shows the Sun-Earth Lagrange point, L1, is about 1.5 million km from the Earth towards the Sun, and there have been many solar observatories located here, including DSCOVR, WIND, SOHO, and ACE.

Based on Newton's formula we have to imagine an object "C" on the line joining the centre of Sun and Earth (A and B). Then we have to solve an equation by equating the force of attraction by the object "C" between the Sun and Earth. We have to use the following Newton's formula of gravitational attraction:

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$$

Now it is simpler and more logical to evaluate visible attractions between planets by using my hypothesis. It is said that satellites are able to orbit around the planet because they are locked into speeds that are fast enough to defeat the downward pull of gravity.

Based on my hypothesis of gravitational attraction there is another explanation for orbiting satellites and planets. Any visible attraction between two objects can be felt after a certain time interval of their presence at a location. And during that time interval, if the objects take new positions, they will deflect the resultant effect of visible attraction by their previous positions. Everyone is aware that when we see an image of a star located several light years away, that star has already moved to a new location and we are watching its fake position at the old location. Similar conditions must be associated with gravitational force, which Newton had not imagined; perhaps he was only watching apples falling on Earth for a visible short distance

To avoid the effect of push between the two objects, one of them has to leave the area enclosed between their common tangents before they experience the effect of push due to their previous positions.

So, in order to understand and estimate visible attractions more precisely, there is a need to re-examine the hypothesis of push by particles.

You won't know whether a thing is perfect or not until it is shown to be imperfect.

We take the Gravity, as described by Newton, for granted.

We are taught about Newton's law of Gravitation in high school.

We solve a variety of questions using the formula given in this law.

We have a complete belief that this law predicts everything accurately.

We think of it as an ultimate description of gravity, something like a default setting.

But neither Newton nor Einstein could imagine that the universe will be found to be expanding.

You might know that planets move around the sun in an elliptical orbit.

Now consider a situation from the frame of reference of the sun.

(Disregard the motion of the sun around the galaxy. Assume it to be stationary and only the planets moving around it).

According to Newton's theory, this ellipse (the orbit of a planet) must remain the same forever. That is, the ellipse should not move at all. It must remain as it is (you can say stationary). The ellipse must not rotate.

This turned out to be true for all planets... except for Mercury.

After observations of the orbit of Mercury, it was found that the elliptical path that it covers rotates with time, along the direction of its revolution around the sun.

The orbital ellipse of Mercury rotates about an arc of 43 seconds per century.

Reference video: <https://qph.cf2.quoracdn.net/main-qimg-48784e9e6f2afeda716eff5b4a8682c9>

It is contradicting the theory of Newton; the ellipse doesn't stay stationary forever.

Newton tried to give a separate theorem to explain this phenomenon. Just like the guys do in chemistry, making a separate rule to explain each phenomenon that gives exceptional behaviour (when other laws of chemistry fail to explain it).

Then there was the General Theory of Relativity for the rescue.

It explained that the ellipse of every planet around the sun must necessarily rotate. This rotation is too small for other planets to be detected, except for mercury. Also, according to Newton's law of gravitation, only bodies with mass face the gravitational force.

But, it was found that light rays are curved by the gravitational field of the sun. And we know that photons (the particle nature of light) don't have mass, but only energy.

Again, the General Theory of Relativity explained that both mass and energy cause and face gravity.

Einstein also assumed that the universe was static [not expanding], and he had added a term to his equations called the cosmological constant that provided a repulsive force to overcome the mutual gravity that would otherwise cause the universe to collapse.

Use of mathematics for scientific explanations need not be required but only for resultant output of an effect. Using any constant in any equation is equivalent to admitting that we don't know some part of the fundamentals.

After Hubble's discovery [that the universe is expanding] Einstein not only withdrew his cosmological constant, but regretted ever putting it in.

Since 1983, I have been trying my best to show my hypothesis to the world. People consider me to be supporting Le Sage's Theory that remained rejected due to his poor representation.

The papers were sent to different departments including the National Physical Laboratory of India but no one was prepared to give any comment. After a long wait, I submitted the thesis to Dr. J. C. Edwards, Editor of the British and American Scientific Research Association, CANADA. I got an immediate response and was advised to approach Dr. W. G. Carnahan, Executive Secretary Association Pushing Gravity Research, U.S.A. And got his response as under:

I was never convinced to accept that there can be any hollow space in the universe.

Another mysterious, very common scientific observation is being taught in the schools without any convincing explanation.

We understand that magnets have two poles and that depending on the orientation of two magnets there can be attraction between the opposite poles or repulsion between similar poles. We recognize that there is some region extending around a magnet where this happens. The magnetic field describes this region. This type of attraction and repulsion can happen anywhere in space.

A simple model depicting the working of magnet

Consider a hollow pipe with a propeller fan fixed in the middle as shown in the diagram.

If this simple model is immersed in stationary water, the propeller will throw a stream of water from the right end of the pipe. The water will flow exactly similar to the pattern of the magnetic field.

If two pipes are placed near to each other as shown in the diagram, the out flowing water stream will create a repulsive force between the two pipes.

And for a reverse position as shown in the diagram, the two pipes will behave as if there is a force of attraction between them. They will move towards each other not due to any sucking effect between their facing ends but due to repulsive force at their extreme ends.

It gives a hint that some unknown matter is involved to generate attraction like behavior between the magnetic poles.

It is also giving some hint that some propeller type mechanism is being performed by the molecular structure of the magnetic matter.

As repulsion can happen anywhere in space, it supports the presence of some unknown matter throughout the universe. If we believe that “to every action there is an equal and opposite reaction”, an object can get a reaction only by another object; and that too in the form of repulsion.

Since the 1920s, astronomers have hypothesized that the universe contains more matter than seen by the naked eye or by the use of any scientific gadgets.

There can be several kinds of dark matter similar to different types of gases in the air. It is noticed, by observing unexplainable movement of galaxies, that the path of motion of galaxies is being influenced by some nearby clusters of invisible matter.

On 25 August 2016, astronomers reported that Dragonfly 44, an ultra diffuse galaxy (UDG) with the mass of the Milky Way galaxy, but with nearly no star structure, is made almost entirely of dark matter.

In 1983, I got the copyright to my research paper for a new gravitational formula based on the assumption that the universe is crowded by the smallest energy packets moving all around with the speed of light.

We know that light travels slowest in denser mediums and also light has a maximum speed limit.

The speed of light in water is 2.25×10^8 meters per second (m/s).

The speed of light in a vacuum is 3×10^8 meters per second, and the speed of light in air is 1.0003 times slower than light in a vacuum, which slows it all the way down from 299,792,458 meters per second to 299,702,547 meters per second.

What we consider as vacuum space may still contain invisible matter that is mostly restricting the speed of light to a certain maximum observed value.

It may be mentioned here that as per a simple observation recorded unknowingly by a CCTV camera, light is found to be traveling faster than the 299,792,458 meters per second. See page 17 of paper "Rishiraj Biofield Effect" available at the following link:

<https://www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2410065.pdf>

The paper can also be found by searching Google "Rishiraj Biofield Effect". This paper is also displaying CCTV recordings of rays resembling light rays but traveling slower than speed of sound. Does it not require proper scientific investigation? Most present time young researchers restrict them to short and quick scientific studies mainly for papers to become PhD to get academic jobs at universities or other positions for a respectful and high paid job. How many PhD seekers have opted for a research proposal related to God, ghosts and their unexplainable recordings by old generation cameras?

Rishiraj Biofield Effect

A unique property of "bio-field" has been discovered. Its radiating energy, during some unique conditions, can create a photoelectric effect but it is not traveling with the speed of light, rather it is found to be moving with extremely variable speeds, many a times faster than speed of light.

The image of his biofield at point "2" is matching with the position of the person when he has not yet reached to location "1". This can only happen when the rays emerging from his biofield are moving faster than speed of light.

When he reached the location "1", his corresponding image of his biofield was already visible at "2" during his previous position.

Light is also seen traveling slower than speed of sound

It can be seen that the outline of the shadow is matching with the position of the person when he was at the location of its previous shadow. This proves that his “bio-field” has released energy waves during his position at the location of chasing shadow. As the energy waves from “bio-field” are traveling with slower speed than light rays, by the time the image of the shadow reaches the camera, the person has moved a little forward, and his real image, traveling with speed of light, also reaches the camera at the same time.

The shadow is matching with his image when he was at the location of the shadow

In 1983, I got a copyright on dark matter type smallest energy packets that are moving in every direction with the speed of light. Based on this concept, a new formula of gravitational force was developed.

Main Text:

THE UNKNOWN TRUTH

Gravitational attraction and the smallest

Since the dawn of civilization the human minds have been baffled on the functioning of the universe. Time and again, theories were proposed by scientists, which were tested against the available observations and accepted till new findings came to light. Each discarded theory was definitely a stepping stone for the next accepted one. Human minds always tend to search for the hidden treasure of unknown facts that nature holds. In this paper I have tried to explain the exact system and mechanism of so called gravitational attraction in a more logical way.

1. GRAVITATION

Gravitational attraction plays an important role in explaining certain astronomical phenomena. Its effects can be predicted and explained, but its ultimate cause is probably as mysterious to us as it was to Newton. Gravitational attraction seems to function instantaneously over immense distances and is unaffected by the presence or absence of barriers between the objects.

Newton has provided us the law of gravitational attraction and Einstein has also developed a competing hypothesis that explains the phenomenon of gravitational attraction in another way; but the two give identical results except when extremely large masses and very great velocities are involved. However, Newton's law of universal gravitation continues to explain most of the everyday phenomena with which we are familiar.

Still a few questions remained unanswered as:

How is the smallest particle of matter able to send the gravitational waves in every corner of the universe, and from where it is getting a continuous energy?

How can a tiny particle create such a strong wave which travels immense distances unaffected by the presence of big stars as barriers?

How does a gravitational wave, when it strikes an object on its way, make it move in the direction from where the wave is coming?

The inward pulling tendency of gravity should make the universe shrink or at the most static. But it is not so as the discovery of the expansion of the universe is observed.

According to Newton's law of gravitation objects attract each other with a force which varies directly as the product of the masses of the two objects and inversely as the square of the distances between them. The total gravitational attraction between the sun and the earth exceeds that between the moon and earth by about 175 times. However, tides are caused by a difference in gravitational attraction on the near and far sides of a body, not by the total pull on it. Quantitatively, the tide producing force varies inversely as the cube of the distance.

I am giving below an example of gravitational attraction based on the Newton's law which explains mathematically:

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$$

Where m_1 is the mass of one body, m_2 that of the other, r the distance between their centers, G the constant of gravitation and F the force with which the bodies attract each other.

In fig. 1, consider six similar cubes of matter lying side by side and each having their mass equal to m grams and sides equal to 1 cm each.

Fig – 1

According to the law of gravitational attraction the force of attraction between 5 and 6, 4 and 6, 3 and 6, 2 and 6 and 1 and 6 will be as under:

$$f_5 = G \frac{m m}{1^2} ,$$

$$f_4 = G \frac{m m}{2^2} ,$$

$$f_3 = G \frac{m m}{3^2} ,$$

$$f_2 = G \frac{m m}{4^2} \text{ and}$$

$$f_1 = G \frac{m m}{5^2}$$

The cubes 1 to 5 are touching each other and can be considered as a single block A-B of 1X5X1 cm with its mass equal to 5 m. The force of attraction between the block A-B and cube 6 will be as under:

$$F = G \frac{m(5m)}{3^2}$$

We know that the F should be equal to $f_1 + f_2 + f_3 + f_4 + f_5$ Therefore,

$$G \frac{m m}{1^2} + G \frac{m m}{2^2} + G \frac{m m}{3^2} + G \frac{m m}{4^2} + G \frac{m m}{5^2} = G \frac{m(5m)}{3^2}$$

Or

$$\frac{1}{1^2} + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{4^2} + \frac{1}{5^2} = \frac{5}{3^2}$$

Or

$$1.46 = 0.56$$

This shows that the gravitational formula is not perfect in the mathematical form also.

I have explained gravitational attraction in another way, more logical, that may explain some unknown phenomena of the universe in simple terms. At present when we see two objects moving towards each other, we presume that they have some system to suck the other. But, the technique they are supposed to be using to attract the other is like a black box magic with no explanation from any institute.

We know that to move an object we will try to push it with our hands rather than make it move behind us without any rope attached to the object. Nature too will adopt the simplest act to accomplish any job. So, if an object can be made to move by push or pull, the act of push which is easier and simple to perform should not be ignored while dealing with formulation of gravitational law. Although the push logic may not simplify every related universal action in one go, it will definitely open a new chapter to solve some ever baffling scientific mysteries.

It can be that the visible attraction of objects is the result of the push they are getting by the bombardment of smallest particles originating from some locations of the universe. Maybe the exploding stars are releasing these particles during their elimination from the universe. They represent a matter state of dying matter. Or, there can be some other type of origin that is releasing these particles.

Consider a single object placed in a space where it is getting equal blows from all sides. The object will remain stationary as the force of push from one side will get neutralized by the force of push from other sides.

The moment another object is placed near the first object; the two will behave as if they are attracting each other. The objects will behave like filters for the push rays for each other. The number of rays that will pass through the objects will depend on the densities of the objects. That is, the force with which the two objects will be pushed towards each other by the push rays will be directly proportional to their densities.

These bombarding particles should be the smallest particles of the universe. An electron can have thousands of them. If an electron can travel in a metallic wire, in the form of electricity, some of these push particles too can pass through the biggest stars. At present it is just an imagination as the complete characteristics of these smallest particles will require more practical studies. It is the fact that they are there and all the vacant space of the universe is occupied by them. Generally they are moving long distances like rays but when they happen to revolve around each other they take the form of matter and start blocking free motion of lone particles.

We have observed electricity moving through extremely long wires. We have found that electric current is the movement of electrons from one end to another end of wire. There is no clarity to suggest if the same electron is moving from one end to the last end of wire or the electrons are kicking successive electrons similar to the following fact.

Ref: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eUSTw8nLfZM>

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Most probably, an electron is transferring electric energy similar to the above observation. And the smallest particle is also behaving in the same manner. It is getting diffused in the matter during collision and the other end of the matter is forced to release a new similar particle. The striking particle remains stored in the matter in some other form of energy.

A study of the resultant effect of push rays on fast moving objects will be more interesting. Every two objects in the universe are producing a kind of shadow between them by blocking push rays from their other sides. Different patterns of shadows are formed by the resultant effect of different shadows by different objects and an object will get a push towards the area of more darkness. For fast moving objects the pattern of a shadow by them will be more complex as the moving objects will create a new shadow for their new position before their previous shadow is eliminated by the push rays coming from all around the universe.

Just consider an event explained below in fig 1 to 5. Let two objects “a” and “b” shown at location “1” appears in the universe at a distance of one light year between them. Since the push rays can be considered to be traveling with the velocity of light, they will experience attraction between them after a period of one year.

Now again consider that these objects start moving parallel to each other with the velocity of light. The shadows of push rays will take the form as shown in fig “6”. That shows that the objects will not have any visible attraction between them. That is, the direction of push between them will be opposite to their path of motion.

Let me explain it more clearly by using Fig-7.

Here the objects are moving with half the velocity of light.

Fig-7

Objects A and B have moved to new positions A' and B' in one second. They are moving parallel to each other with half the velocity of light. The pushing particles which were striking A at x and B at y have reached x' and y' during the period in which A has reached A' and B has reached B'. Similarly A' and B' are continuously unblocking the path of striking particles behind their previous positions. This will create a shadow of reduced pressure as shown by sky blue colour. The objects will experience force of push towards this reduced pressure area. That is, visible attraction between the objects will take a 45 degree turn.

The explanation of phenomena of elliptical movement of planets around the sun, circulation of moon around the earth or for geostationary satellites etc. the centrifugal and centripetal forces are said to be playing the main role.

We generally explain that the gravitational attraction develops centripetal force for the revolving object and its motion develops centrifugal force pulling it outward. When both the forces are equal and opposite, the revolving object maintains its stationary orbit.

But the same events can also be explained entirely differently by the push rays hypothesis. The movement of satellites around larger bodies may be following a different rule of changing to new position before the effect of mutually blocked push rays takes place at their previous positions. As already explained earlier, if we consider two objects suddenly appear in the universe at a distance of one light year, the effect of push between them will only start after a year, and in the meantime if we consider the next options:

(1) In the meantime if these two objects move to new positions which are away from the area enclosed between their common tangents of their previous positions, they will escape the effect of push between them.

(2) If one of the objects remain within the area of their common tangents and the second object disappears after staying for one hour, the first object will get a push towards the old location of the second object for one hour after the lapse of one year.

(3) If only some part of one object remains in the area of common tangents of their previous positions, the force of push between them will be directly proportional to only those masses which exist in the previous area of darkness. Also, part of the object, which escapes the previous area of darkness, will try to retain its previous state of motion. The resultant of two forces under suitable selections of their masses, distances and previous motions can again make them stationary with respect to each other.

(4) To avoid the effect of push between the two objects, one of them has to leave the area enclosed between their common tangents before they experience the effect of push due to their previous positions. The maximum time limit to leave the area of effect will be equal to time taken by the push rays to travel from one object to the other (velocity of push rays is same as velocity of light). Therefore, speed of a satellite for its orbit can be worked out as explained next:

$$S = R \frac{M.m.V}{D}$$

Here S is the speed of the satellite, M is the mass of the earth, m is the mass of the satellite, V is the velocity of light, D is the distance between the satellite and the centre of the earth and R is a constant.

Here “M” and “m” are representing proportional value of diameters of earth and satellite.

The hypothesis also explains that the orbit of a satellite will get disturbed if it is to cross the area of common tangents between the earth and moon or any nearby planet. The disturbance in the orbit of the satellite will be because the push rays that are pushing it towards the earth will get weakened by the moon when all the three are in a straight line. It will be better to select the orbit of the satellite that does not cross the area of common tangents of the nearby planets.

Scientists have known for a long time that there appears to be 'too much' gravity in the Universe. They can observe the effects of gravitational forces at work, but the origin of these forces cannot be identified. In fact, as shown in the figure, the gravitational push rays are coming from remote areas from some locations responsible for their release, and many planets that are obstructing their passage are disturbing their force of push that we detect without knowing the actual reason.

New Gravitational formula

$$F = K . m_1 m_2 \Theta$$

Force of attraction F between two spherical objects with masses m_1 and m_2 is equal to push constant K multiplied by product of masses and angle of their common intersecting tangent.

Mathematical derivation of formula

On the assumption of the hypothesis of push rather than attraction I have worked out the new gravitational formula. We know that every matter in the universe consists of a few scores of more elementary particles, and all particles have got some mass. There must be a smallest particle capable of blocking a single push particle. I will call them 'Anu'. Anu is the smallest particle in the form of matter having some mass and the push particles are still smaller with almost zero mass.

Area of the element = Circumference multiplied by width

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 2\pi y \cdot EC \\
 &= 2\pi y \cdot r \cdot d\theta \\
 &= 2\pi r \cdot y \cdot d\theta \quad \text{---(i)}
 \end{aligned}$$

It is clear from the figure that

$$\begin{aligned}
 y &= r \cos \theta \\
 x &= r \sin \theta
 \end{aligned}$$

Differentiating, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 dx &= r \cos \theta \cdot d\theta \\
 &= y d\theta
 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting $dx = y d\theta$ in ---(i), we have

Area of the element = $2\pi r dx$

Force on the element = $\frac{M}{4\pi r^2} \cdot 2\pi r dx$

$$= \frac{M}{2r} \cdot dx \quad \text{---(ii)}$$

Here the two push rays MN and KN of equal strength are striking the Anu N. The rays are equally inclined to the line joining the centers of A and B. Their resultant effect on Anu N will be towards the centre of object B because their perpendicular resultants NG and NH will cancel each other. The total resultant effect of both rays MN and KN towards B will be $2\cos \theta$ times their total strength. Therefore, the resultant of a single ray MN towards B will be equal to $\cos \theta$ times its total strength.

The element EFDC is just like the circumference of a circle which is forming base of a cone with its vertex at N. The force on the element EFDC by the push rays is concentrating at N because these are travelling towards N. Their resultant effect will be towards centre of B, and will be $\cos \theta$ times the total strength of the rays.

Therefore, resultant force at N by the push rays passing through the element EFDC and striking at N:

$$= \cos \theta \cdot \frac{M}{2r} \cdot dx$$

$$= \frac{x}{r} \cdot \frac{M}{2r} \cdot dx$$

$$= \frac{M}{2r^2} \cdot x \cdot dx$$

Resultant force on N by all the push rays which are passing through the complete cap EF

$$= \frac{M}{2r^2} \int_x^r x \cdot dx = \frac{M}{2r^2} \left[\frac{x^2}{2} \right]$$

$$= \frac{M}{2r^2} \left[\frac{r^2}{2} - \frac{x^2}{2} \right] = \frac{M}{4} \left[1 - \left(\frac{x}{r} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$= \frac{M}{4} \left[1 - \cos^2 \theta \right]$$

$$= \frac{M}{4} \sin^2 \theta \quad \text{————— (iii)}$$

Here 'M' can also be explained as the total force experienced by the smallest Anu when the push rays are striking it from all sides, and from (iii) we get the force experienced by Anu N in presence of a object B which is supposed to be completely blocking the push rays that are trying to pass through its body and reach Anu N. The value of M is constant for every location of the universe. It is the highest possible force per unit area that can ever be created. In fact, it may be the effect of force M that we recognize in different forms of forces. But, in this universe, which is crowded by unlimited floating objects, there can't be a place where we can have full strength of push rays concentration.

I have considered that object B is having the highest possible density to completely block the push rays. In case of lighter density, some push rays will pass through it and strike the Anu N. This will neutralize the effect of some push rays which are pressing Anu from the right side, and that will make it less attractive to object B. So, the force with which Anu will be pushed towards B will depend on the density of B and will increase as the density will increase.

∴ Force of attraction between N and B ∝ Density of B (iv)

The force will also increase if the volume of b is increased.

∴ Force of attraction between N and B ∝ Volume of B (V)

Now, in the figure shown below, let us suppose that there is another object C lying between the lines NM and NK. The density of C is much lower than the density of N, but its volume and density are enough to block all the push rays trying to reach object B after passing through the location of N. The resultant force on C by rays coming between NM and NK will be the same as on Anu N. But, if the density of C is further reduced, more push rays will pass through it making it less attractive to B. Therefore, the force of attraction between b and C will also be directly proportional to density and volume of object C.

∴ Force of attraction between B and C:

\propto Density of C (Vi)

\propto Volume of C (Vii)

$$f = \frac{M}{4} \sin^2 \theta_1$$

or $f \propto \sin^2 \theta_1$ (∵ M is constant)

$f \propto D_1$ (Density of B)

$f \propto V_1$ (Volume of B)

$f \propto D_2$ (Density of C)

$f \propto V_2$ (Volume of C)

∴ $f \propto D_1 V_1 D_2 V_2 \sin^2 \theta_1$

$f \propto m_1 m_2 \sin^2 \theta_1$ ——— (Viii)

In the equation (Viii) I have taken into consideration only those push rays which are passing through a single point N and are coming between the lines NM and NK. We can see from the figure that these are not the only rays affecting the two objects B and C. All other rays travelling between the lines ST and UV are also responsible for the visible attraction between the two objects B and C. Now I will work out the effect of another set of push rays which are travelling between the lines St and UV. Now consider the figure given below. I have extended the lines ST and UV of the previous figure.

The lines ST and UV are crossing at N'. Suppose C' is the other position of object C. Here C and C' are serving as similar filters for all the push rays passing through the point N' and travelling between the lines ST and UV only. The rays will produce the same effect on the object C as these will produce on C'. By using equation (Viii) the force (f') between B and C by all the rays which are passing through the point N' can be worked out to be the same as between B and C'

$$\therefore f' \propto m_1 m_2 \sin^2 \theta_2 \quad \text{———— (ix)}$$

The line X' Y' is passing through the centers of B and C. This line is supposed to be reaching the end of the universe on both sides. N and N' are the only two points on the line X' Y' which are taken into consideration to work out the resultant effect of push rays which are passing through them along with the objects B and C. We can see that the line X' Y' is nothing but a series of points similar to N and N' from where the other set of push rays can pass and effect the two objects B and C. Now, I will work out the effect of all the push rays passing through B and C while crossing from each point on the line X' Y'.

If I rotate the tangent ST anticlockwise over the circumference of object C till it becomes parallel to X'Y', the angle θ_2 will become equal to zero, or the point N' will go to the end of universe towards the right hand side. Therefore, the resultant force by all the push rays crossing the line N'Y' and the object B and C will be as under:

$$F \propto m_1 m_2 \int_0^{\theta_2} \sin^2 \theta_2 \cdot d\theta \quad \text{———— (X)}$$

Now again, if I rotate tangent LM clockwise over the circumference of object C till it becomes parallel to X'Y', angle θ_1 will become zero, or point N will go to the end of the universe towards the left hand side. Therefore, the resultant of all the push rays crossing the line X'N and the object B and C will be as under

$$F' \propto m_1 m_2 \int_0^{\theta_1} \sin^2 \theta_1 \cdot d\theta \quad \text{———— (XI)}$$

Similarly if N is moved to N', angle θ_1 will become equal to angle θ_2 . Therefore, the resultant of all the push rays crossing NN' and object B and C will be as under

$$F'' \propto m_1 m_2 \int_{\theta_2}^{\theta_1} \sin^2 \theta_1 \cdot d\theta \quad \text{———— (XII)}$$

Adding equation (X), (XI) and (XII) we get

$$F + F' + F'' \propto m_1 m_2 \int_0^{\theta_2} \sin^2 \theta_2 \cdot d\theta + m_1 m_2 \int_0^{\theta_1} \sin^2 \theta_1 \cdot d\theta + m_1 m_2 \int_{\theta_2}^{\theta_1} \sin^2 \theta_1 \cdot d\theta$$

Or

Force of attraction between the objects B and C is

$$\propto m_1 m_2 \left[\int_0^{\theta_2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\theta_2 - \frac{\sin 2\theta_2}{2} \right) + C \right) + \int_0^{\theta_1} \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\theta_1 - \frac{\sin 2\theta_1}{2} \right) + C \right) + \int_{\theta_2}^{\theta_1} \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\theta_1 - \frac{\sin 2\theta_1}{2} \right) + C \right) \right]$$

$$\text{Or Total Force} \propto m_1 m_2 \left(\theta_1 - \frac{\sin 2\theta_1}{2} + 2C \right)$$

$$\text{Or Total Force} \propto m_1 m_2 \left(2\theta_1 - \sin 2\theta_1 + 4C \right)$$

Here RHS is multiplied by 2 which is constant.

$$\text{Or Force} = K \cdot m_1 m_2 (\theta - \sin \theta)$$

Here $2\theta_1$ is equal to θ which is the angle formed by the two intersecting tangents common to both the objects B and C, m_1 and m_2 are their respective masses and K is a constant.

I have assumed that all the push rays passing through the spherical objects will get the uniform resistance; rays passing near the edges will get less resistance compared to the centre of the spherical object.

The formula worked out will get some percentage of error. But the percentage of deviation of force value can be considered to be the same for the same shape of objects and constant 'K' will neutralise the error effect. Also, we can eliminate $\sin\Theta$ which is very small compared to Θ .

$$\therefore F = K \cdot m_1 m_2 \Theta$$

Comparison of old and new formula by analyzing variation of force between two objects for variable distances.

It is clear from Newton's formula of gravitational attraction and from the new formula of universal push that the two objects will lose the visible attraction as the distance between them is increased.

According to Newton the force of attraction will be inversely proportional to the square of the distance between the centers of the two objects. And by the new formula the attraction will be directly proportional to the angle between the two intersecting tangents common to both the objects. I would like to show the comparison of different values of force of attraction by both the formulas for two objects at variable distances.

In the figure shown below objects A and B of 2 cm diameter each are lying with their centers x cm apart. Angle Θ is formed by their two intersecting tangents.

From above we can calculate different values of Θ and $1/x^2$ for different values of x. Table shown below displays these values for x ranging from 2 cm to 21 cm.

Comparison of old and new formula by analyzing variation of force between two objects for variable distances.

Sl. No.	X	\odot	$1/x^2$	$270(1/x^2)$
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.
1.	2	180°	0.25000	180
2.	3	83°36'	0.11110	79.98
3.	4	60°	0.06250	45.00
4.	5	47°12'	0.04000	28.80
5.	6	39°	0.02778	20.01
6.	7	33°12'	0.02041	14.69
7.	8	29°	0.01562	11.25
8.	9	25°42'	0.01235	8.89
9.	10	23°4'	0.01000	7.20
10.	11	21°	0.008264	5.95
11.	12	19°12'	0.006944	4.99
12.	13	17°38'	0.005917	4.26
13.	14	16°24'	0.005101	3.67
14.	15	15°15'	0.004444	3.20
15.	16	14°24'	0.003906	2.81
16.	17	13°30'	0.003460	2.49
17.	18	12°38'	0.003087	2.22
18.	19	12°04'	0.002770	2.00
19.	20	11°28'	0.002500	1.80
20.	21	10°56'	0.002268	1.60

The column 5 of the above table is worked out by multiplying all the values of column 4 by 720. The column 5 is required to bring the initial value of $1/x^2$ equal to \odot i.e., 180 for the purpose of comparison by plotting in the form of curves. The data of column 3 and 5 is plotted for values of X of column 2 and is shown on the next page.

Fig shows two curves for column 3 and 5 for different values of X. From the two curves we can see that the rate of change of visible attraction with respect to distance is almost similar by both the methods. But for long distances, we are underestimating the force of attraction by using Newton's gravitational formula. Since there was no other better way to explain attraction between the objects except Newton's gravitational formula, the blueprint of the arrangement of most of the universal objects was developed by its use. For derivation of mass of sun, moon etc. we have used Newton's gravitational equation that has failed to explain some basic questions on tides. If total gravitational attraction between the sun and the earth exceeds that between the moon and earth by about 175 times, why is the sun not creating tides?

Attraction between non-spherical objects

To get the value of θ for non-spherical objects, their equivalent volume of spherical objects is to be used.

Neutral space between the two objects

In the figure shown above, **A** and **B** are two objects of mass m_1 and m_2 . A third object **C** of mass m is lying between **A** and **B**. θ_1 is the angle of two intersecting tangents of **A** and **C**, θ_2 is the angle of two intersecting tangents of **C** and **B**.

$$\text{Force of attraction between A and C} = K \frac{m_1 m}{\theta_1}$$

$$\text{Force of attraction between C and B} = K \frac{m_2 m}{\theta_2}$$

If **C** is lying at the neutral space we get

$$K \frac{m_1 m}{\theta_1} = K \frac{m_2 m}{\theta_2}$$

$$\text{Or } \theta_1 = \frac{m_2}{m_1} \cdot \theta_2$$

Determination of the constant K

The push constant 'K' can be determined in the laboratory by the same experiments that were used to get gravitational constant.

Effect of a moving object between the two objects

In the figure (I) shown below, A is an object representing earth and S is a small object representing a satellite which is rotating around A in an exact circular orbit. Now in figure (II) let there be another object B that appears near A. Let B be similar to the moon. The circular orbit of S will take the shape as shown in Fig (II). Here the orbit of the satellite is not passing through the line joining the centre of A and B.

But, if the path of S is such that it exactly passes through the line joining the centre of A and B, the orbit will get distorted as shown in fig (III). The object S will get sudden jerk of push towards B when it will be crossing at M. The same

Effect of a comparatively smaller magnitude will be observed at the location L.

These disturbances at L and M for S will be caused because the push rays which are pushing it towards A are suddenly blocked by B when S is passing between the area of their common tangents.

Push particles may be the ultimate building block of the universe

Although we have not yet discovered the smallest particle of the universe, yet we can assume that there must be smallest particles that are the ultimate building blocks of the universe. There may be only two shapes of basic fundamental particles and not necessarily in the spherical forms. In my opinion the push particles that are responsible for visible attraction, so called the gravitational attraction, are the smallest particles. The Anus that I used to derive the new gravitational formula is the smallest particle in the form of matter that can block a striking push particle. And the Anu is formed by few push particles. A single push particle will not be traceable by any scientific means but by observing the force by its impact on bigger particles.

There must be some sources in the universe responsible for their release. Maybe, the dying star melts away in the form of these push particles. Or, during any blast of matter, some part of matter disintegrates to the extent to release its basic building blocks free. In our universe, unaccounted stars and galaxies are disappearing the way ice melts away in water. In fact, most of the pictures of galaxies show that there was a big blast of gigantic objects that is breaking it to dust of stars etc along with flames of a variety of radiations and the smallest push particles.

The black holes (objects) continue to suck surrounding stars etc till the matter at their centre continues to bear the extreme pressure. At some critical pressure the matter at their centre explodes like nuclear bombs and these results in the formation of new galaxies. So, the galaxies are vanishing to black holes and black holes blast to new galaxies. The main role for these periodic changes between black holes and galaxies is associated with the push particles that are not only the building blocks of matter, gravitational attraction but also for the complete journey of the universe.

It is my intuitive guess that in the early life of the universe there must be pure single element planets for every element of our periodic table. **We may still find some pure diamond stars, gold stars, silver stars, water stars etc.** Making and breaking of galaxies and black holes is creating planets of mixed elements.

Life came to our earth from some other planet and will move on to many other planets. Just imagine the case when our earth will break-up in several pieces after some gigantic asteroid will hit it. Many living creatures, plant seeds will be carried away to remote places of the universe packed with frozen sea water. Some ice packed carriers of living cells will find a new earth waiting to begin its civilization.

Life began on ice?

Water & Organics Began Journey to Earth on Icy Particles, Say Researchers.

In the majority of pictures showing galaxies a unique common feature is visible. There are two blast locations just opposite to each other. In the above picture 'A' and 'B' are the main locations from where the debris is being thrown out.

It appears as if a powerful volcano type eruption begins from one end of a black hole type object. The powerful force by blast at one end pushes the molten lava at the centre to the opposite end and another volcano type eruption begins on the other side simultaneously. After some light years of time, the black object breaks up to several stars. Similar millions of events are continually occurring all over the universe and a constant stream of fundamental push particles are getting released.

Since there are countless continuous explosions that are pushing other objects away, the universe should expand as is already observed. Expansion of the universe is a major observed phenomenon that is against Newton's fundamental reasoning to believe in sucking between two objects. Newton or his supporters have not yet explained the mechanism by which the two objects are supposed to be attracting each other. Gravitational attraction is just a statement on observation that we have to believe as there was no other better scientific explanation. The gravitational formula has survived since long and is still being used in present day cosmological studies as its results fall very close to actual observations for short distances that were actually used to drive gravitational constant 'G'. For long distances, generally for computation of masses of stars etc we may be having about 10 to 40 % error.

Image at Sl.No. 7 is the real observation. Similarly, the image on the right side is said to be a real observation of a galaxy.

Images 1 to 6 and 8 are imaginary that show the possible sequences of emergence and elimination of a galaxy that was initially a dense object (maybe a black hole).

Transmission and formation of different rays

We know that the speed of waves throughout the entire frequency range (in vacuum) is the same as the speed of light. This shows that all the waves are dependent on some common factor which is responsible for their speed. Whether two different kinds of waves are produced by entirely two different methods, they have their common property of fixed speed in vacuum. This shows that the speed of a wave may be due to some independent factor which is already present in the universe. Or, something with its own speed is already present which helps carry the energy of different patterns of waves. The universe is not as complex as we presume it by analyzing it by our many complex equations. A little wrong beginning takes us in an entirely different direction. We can also assume that every space of the universe is filled with the push particles moving in all directions with the speed of light.

There is also a possibility that these particles are not actually moving in a straight line but are vibrating in different unique patterns and passing their pattern of motions to their surrounding particles, just like a ripple of water. The ripple of water is a two dimensional phenomena whereas push particles may be creating ripples in three dimensional space.

It may look strange as how a push particle can move so fast in a straight line path when its entire passage is blocked with similar particles. Maybe push particles are not like spherical objects. They may resemble a small piece of spring coil and their path of motion should resemble the structure of that spring coil.

Their surface is almost frictionless and is covering straight passages but is forced to move in a spiral passage by the push particles coming from different directions. As push particles coming from all directions cannot pass from a single point location, they have to move in a spiral passage to give way to other particles coming from all other directions. They do not lose their speed after hitting an Anu as they don't have any mass or momentum and are moving by the push by similar particles just behind them. The push particles moving behind each other in a spiral path forms a push ray which can be considered to be the finest possible ray of our universe. They can generate the highest possible force per unit area during any obstacle in their path of motion.

When a push ray passes through a burning flame it picks up some free particles of the flame and carries them along with it at its own speed. Thus the push rays that are dragging along some particles from flame represent a light ray. Similarly different types of rays are formed depending upon the type of medium through which push rays are passing.

We cannot forget the havoc caused by the cyclonic storms and tornadoes on our earth. These phenomena even today treat strong structures as paper toys. Science has some answers, though they are far from perfect and at least can only help in advance warning to some extent.

We believe that all meteorological phenomena are due to low and high pressures of the atmosphere which are caused by the irregular heating of the air by the sun. Only tides are supposed to be an exceptional process mainly associated with the position of the moon. The rotation of the air currents in the cyclones or tornadoes are believed to be due to the rotation of the earth. Many lives have been lost due to cloud bursts in different parts of the world. A cloud burst is a sudden condensation of water vapours of the cloud in a very short time. Many of us were of the view that cloudburst takes place in mountainous areas where dense clouds get trapped between high mountains and more saturated clouds continue to reach there from a funnel type entrance. But, as we have observed the cloud bursts in plain areas too, there may be some other factor as well to trigger a cloud burst.

Every one must have watched how particles of smoke get uniformly distributed in a closed room in due course of time. Similarly, the law of diffusion helps gases get uniformly distributed in an open space. But, this is not the case with clouds as their molecular structure takes different shapes depending on the temperature and pressure of space from where the wind is passing. Mostly, we give more importance to temperature and humidity than the distribution of pressures for critical meteorological events. The meteorological observatories are generally equipped to record wind direction, humidity, temperature and rainfall. We don't give much importance to gravitational pressure variations on hourly observation basis along with other general observations.

There are some meteorological events like tornados which last only for less than an hour. The destruction caused by a tornado is by its violent winds, by the tremendous lifting effect of updrafts, and by the explosive effect of a sudden drop in the atmospheric pressure. Winds may whirl around the low pressure centre of a tornado at the rates up to 200 to 400 Km./hr. or even more. Updrafts associated with tornadoes may attain speeds of 100 to 200 Km./hr., and thus it acts as a giant vacuum cleaner. Barometer pressure may

drop greatly as 1 to 2 inches of a mercurial barometer. Thus within 10 to 20 seconds pressure may change by as much as 400 lb/Sq.ft., and closed buildings explode outward, roofs are blown off and objects like cars are blown away like tree leaves.

Just how tornadoes originate is still uncertain, and their precise locations cannot be forecast. These sudden meteorological events must not always be associated with the heating of the air by the sun but may be due to some sudden changes of pressures in localised areas under well defined boundaries. At least one event can be mentioned here where some unique observations were made during a full solar eclipse. Change in weather was observed on 16th Feb. 1980 during a full solar eclipse at the Meenambakkam weather observatory which recorded a sudden fall of 2.5 degree centigrade in temperature between 3 and 4 p.m. The humidity was up by 12 percent and the atmospheric pressure dropped by 0.5 millibars.

These observations show that the rise in humidity may be due to the fall of temperature and pressure. And the fall of temperature may be due to the expansion of the air molecules. All these changes can be associated with sudden fall of gravitational field at the localised place of eclipsed area. So, the push ray particles that can be mainly responsible for change of gravitational field within well defined boundaries may be responsible for such extreme short lived localised events.

The pressure of the air at different layers of the atmosphere is due to the weight of the air molecules. And we know that the weight of air molecules is due to the so called gravitational attraction between the earth and the molecules of air. In fact the weight of air molecules is due to the resultant force on them by the push rays coming from all over the universe. These push rays, just like light rays, are forming eclipse-like shadows of low pressure areas not only by the sun and moon but by some other nearby planets too. The paths of many tornadoes are more likely to follow a definite straight line pattern just like solar eclipse shadow paths as they may be caused by some unique position of three or more heavenly bodies.

So, I believe that the variation of the gravitational field plays a great role in some of the major meteorological events. The gravitational field, which is due to the push rays of the universe, falls suddenly on a very limited area on the surface of the earth when the affected area receives weak intensity of push rays due to two or more heavenly objects coming in straight line with that area.

Determination of low pressure area by floating weights

We have seen that the low or high pressures of the atmosphere can also be due to variation in the gravitational field. The gravitational field is continually changing everywhere, even on every localised location of earth similar to temperature variations; though the variation may be too small. Different gravimeters are already there to find out gravitational attraction at a particular place, but they are costly instruments and cannot be utilised in sufficient numbers just like rain gauges. At present their need is not felt in important meteorological events all over the world and, I think, they were not even used in the study of the solar eclipse of 16-02-1980. Even if the gravitational field of a place is changing in the range of 5 % it is sufficient to induce a cloud burst in a homogeneously saturated cloud. Only a careful study of variation of gravitational field and atmospheric pressure over a wide range of area can reveal the relation between the two.

At present we are using barometers, radars and satellites to record low pressures over an area. A barometer tells us the pressure of the atmosphere where it is installed; the radars help us to find out the area of low or high pressures at distant places generally over the sea and by satellites we can take the photographs of circulating clouds which represent the low pressure areas. The radars and the satellites are not helpful if there is not sufficient moisture in the low pressure areas.

Here I am going to explain a very simple instrument which can detect low pressure areas not only on the sea but also on lands where moisture is not present. The instrument is based on the assumption that the majority of low or high pressures are due to variation of the gravitational field as a result of change in intensity of push particle rays. To locate the place of low gravitational field or the low pressure area at least two instruments at two different locations will be required.

Our earth is not responsible for any variation of gravitational field over its surface and the variations can be due to the presence of other heavenly bodies which are always changing their positions with respect to the earth. The tides in the sea are an example of a low gravitational field. In the low gravitational field every particle will reduce its mass.

At the low gravitational field centre every particle of the matter will get a lifting effect in the direction just perpendicular to the surface of earth, and the objects located around the centre will get the lifting effect in the direction slightly inclined towards the low field area. As we go away from the low gravitational field area the direction of the lifting effect of the particles will get more and more inclined towards the gravitational field centre.

In the floating weight instrument a heavy piece of metal is kept in a container to let it float freely in a water filled box. The base of the floating container is tied with the centre of the water container by a very light and flexible spring. Technically the floating weight should remain stationary at the centre of the liquid filled box. But, we can notice that at certain small time intervals, the floating weight will shift its position and the change of position can be due to change of gravitational field. It will shift towards a low gravitational field area or the area of low intensity of push rays.

A careful study of movements of floating weights at several locations all over the earth can reveal new facts which can be helpful in solving the puzzling problems of meteorology as well as everyday science.

Energy changes during the real present time

When we explain speed, velocity, acceleration or momentum we are talking of displacement of an object from one location to another in a certain time interval. This is the fundamental base for all laws of physics, which is the mother of all scientific theories.

To explain the change of position for any object, we need to have another object so that it acts like a reference point to measure the displacement of a moving object. If a person is walking in the compartment of a moving train, we can measure his speed with respect to the persons sitting in the train and also with respect to the buildings outside the train. Both the speeds will be different. Also, the same object will have unlimited no of speeds with respect to all the planets of our universe.

So, if we imagine that only a single object is present in our universe and there is not a single grain of any other particle with which we can compare its motion, the object can be considered either moving or stationary. Most probably, by our present established scientific laws, we can justify it to be stable with respect to its own position.

Next, if we consider two objects, exactly similar to each other, located in the space and maintaining a fix distance from each other. The objects can be considered to be rotating around an imaginary point located exactly at the centre of their distance from each other. If we know the mass of the objects, we can calculate their rate of spin by using gravitational constant. But, the objects can also be considered to be moving parallel to each other in the same direction with the velocity of light. As explained earlier, the push rays suggest that an object, if moving with the speed of light, will defy interference by another object.

Now, the displacement of any object can't be explained purely on the basis of change of distance with respect to some other object. It should also associate it with the time interval during which displacement occurs. Time is a system of measurement that we have devised to assign a value related to the period of any happening. It is mainly used to measure the length of time period between two happenings, and also the time of any happening. The following are simple examples where time is an important factor to explain an event.

1. It has been raining for the last two hours.
2. It was raining for two hours.
3. It is raining

S.No. 1 and 3 are related to the same event and S.No 2 is mentioning a past event. So an event can be a past event or a combination of past and present event, which explains the present real state of the event. The time period of the present, which is a live period for any event to change its state, is so small that our great scientists never thought to explain it. The time period of the present can't be zero else our complete universe would have been like a huge sculpture without any motion of even its fundamental particles.

The present time period is a period during which the smallest fundamental particle when moving with maximum possible speed, very close to velocity of light, covers a distance equivalent to its diameter. To make the universe move, the smallest particle of the universe must take its new position and should be in position to change to the next new position for the coming future time.

The present time can be actually termed as live time for formulation of any action (LTFA). All action or reactions should begin and end within the living time. The living time frame is moving towards the future while sweeping and holding the complete universe for a minimum time equivalent to (LTFA).

The universe is alive, or existing, only for a period of living time period and all its past activities till the live time period are only a history, but that too exist in some memory patterns in the successive living time intervals. Nothing is there before or after LTFA. So, for a smallest particle, moving from A to C (past present to future), it will be available to act or communicate with another particle during its position at B (present) only if the second particle is also close enough to reach it during the present time interval.

How exactly we can draw the boundaries between past, present and future is not so simple since any minute present time dimension can be further sliced to smaller segments of past, present and future. That is, any present hour of time is a representation of the present minute along with 59 minutes from past and future. And similar is the case with a minute or a second and so on. In a broader sense, we don't have any present that can be represented by a certain time period. It seems to be non-existent. If it appears to be non-existent, where do we stand? Do we live in the past, as the future is just a guess?

No, the present does exist, but its time interval is too small that we have not yet imagined. My opinion for the present time is as under:

Present Time Interval = Diameter of the smallest particle/velocity of light

The speed of light is 299,792,458 metres per second.

The diameter of the proton is 0.00000000000002 meters. Or, 2×10^{-14} .

The diameter of the smallest push particle is likely to be many times smaller than the diameter of the proton.

So, the time period of any physical action or chemical reaction that actually takes place in its complete form is too small to get recorded.

When we are observing any event, we are in fact observing the series of past events that happened within successive living time frames but in such a unique way that all the past events are fused to one form of event to make the complete scene alive for LTFA. The brain is only storing the present data by replacing the space of past data, but at the same time present and past are mixed to create a third type of data as we can be conscious of only one frame of events during LTFA.

Now when we explain momentum we say that an object in motion is said to have momentum. This momentum is a vector. It has a size and a direction. The size of the momentum is equal to the mass of the object multiplied by the object's velocity. The direction of the momentum is the same as the direction of the object's velocity. The momentum is an energy that can be converted to other forms of energies.

Now just consider that the universe has only two objects A and B and not a grain of any third particle. Let object A be of 10000 grams and object B of 1 gram. If the distance between the two objects is reducing, we can imagine that either object A is moving towards B or object B is moving towards A. Next possibility is that both may be moving towards each other.

Now consider that object B is fixed to some imaginary wall in space and object A is going to strike it with a velocity of 100 Km per sec. Similarly, consider object A is fixed and object B is going to strike it with the same velocity of 100 Km per sec.

As per our present scientific laws, object 'B' will have greater force of impact on it when it is being hit by 'A' rather than when it hits object 'B' with the same velocity. But, in the absence of any third object in the universe, our present scientific laws are not sufficient to measure the energy due to momentum of a moving object. In this particular example, although their movement can be recorded to be exactly the same in any of the two situations yet they will behave differently during a collision with each other.

We have to find a system that can calculate the quantity of energy stored in a moving object independent of any other object around it. We need to explain momentum with respect to the living time frame of the universe.

For an object, its stored energy due to momentum is not exactly dependent on the total distance travelled by it but on the total resultant effect of the sum of momentum energy by all the smallest particles of the object. But, we know that the smallest particles of the object can't move exactly with the same velocity and direction as they are having their own pattern of motions. During the live time period, which is the real time for a live activity, the majority of fundamental particles may not be moving in the same direction in which the object is moving.

During change of motion of an object, the force of momentum will also try to displace the spiral rotation of fundamental particles of the object. Energy never gets lost as it can only change from one form to another. That is, the energy due to momentum is likely to be preserved or utilized in the object for shifting fundamental particles to some new positions just like creating potential energy by shifting any object to any height.

If we can devise some system that can change the behaviour of fundamental particles to mimic like an object in motion, the complete object should start moving.

Human biofield has the capacity to influence its surroundings. According to some practitioners, biofield therapies stimulate a healing response by affecting subtle energy fields that surround the human body.

During the act of hypnotizing too the role of bio-field will be found to be the main player. The bio-field of the hypnotizer can be found to be extending its area to cover persons willing to get hypnotized. All the persons who have willingly got disconnected from their respective bio-field can start obeying instructions from the hypnotizer's bio-field.

In the near future evidence will be available to suggest that matter too has its own bio-field type field and humans can learn to utilise their bio-field to influence the bio-field of the matter. There is a scope for humans to use their bio-field energy to change the behaviour property of the "Anu" of matter and induce momentum energy without any external physical force.

Can human bio-field also interfere with the binding forces of the matter?

Ref: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uri_Geller

Can a curse change someone to a lifeless stone?

Ref: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ahalya>

Can a human bio-field continue to effect matter after death?

Ref: “Rishiraj Biofield Effect” <https://www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2410065.pdf>